

VISTLE

IMMERSIVE WIND FARM VISUALISATION FOR SMARTER ENERGY PLANNING

WHAT IS VISTLE?

Vistle is an **open-source scientific visualisation platform** designed for immersive and interactive analysis of large-scale simulation datasets. Developed for high-performance computing (HPC) environments, the software **supports real-time exploration of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations** and complex three-dimensional infrastructure models across desktop, augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) systems.

Within MERIDIONAL, Vistle was used to create a collaborative **digital twin** capable of integrating airflow simulations, terrain models and wind farm infrastructure into a unified virtual environment. The platform also supports multiple scientific data standards and remote collaboration workflows.

Vistle source code
available on GitHub

<https://github.com/vistle/vistle>

HOW IT WORKS

The prototype integrates airflow simulations generated with different CFD solvers, three-dimensional wind farm models and immersive rendering technologies into a single navigable environment. To manage large territorial datasets, the system uses level of detail (LOD) rendering methods that dynamically optimise visual com-

KitePower Kite Visualization in the CAVE (a walkable room combined with six projected plexiglasses that combined with 3D shutter glasses creates a 3D experience)

plexity according to user position and visibility.

The platform supports both conventional desktop access and immersive systems such as CAVE (Cave Automatic Virtual Environment) installations, **enabling flexible collaboration between distributed research and industrial teams.**

WHAT IT CHANGES

The prototypes demonstrate **how immersive visualisation and digital twin technologies** can improve understanding of **offshore wind operations and simulation data**. By transforming complex aerodynamic information into interactive visual experiences, the platform supports more efficient collaboration between engineers, researchers and industrial stakeholders.

Its open-source and interoperable architecture also strengthens future scalability and industrial adoption across the European renewable energy ecosystem.

Airflow around a wind turbine

WHAT WAS ACHIEVED

The project delivered a working prototype for remote interactive visualisation of offshore wind farms using immersive VRy technologies. The environment successfully combines CFD airflow simulations with three-dimensional infrastructure models and large-scale terrain rendering.

MERIDIONAL project delivered:

- **1 functional immersive prototype** for remote wind farm visualisation;
- **1 digital twin of the He Dreiht offshore wind farm;**
- **1 digital twin of the WINSSENT test site,** integrating lidar and UAV data;
- **visualisation of KitePower trajectory datasets** inside a user-selected digital terrain model;
- **visualisation of turbulence, airflow, air pressure and air density** around a wind blade;
- **detailed turbulence visualisation** around wind blade structures;
- support for **multiple scientific simulation formats;**
- compatibility with **desktop, AR, VR and CAVE systems;**
- optimisation for **large-scale datasets** through Level of Detail rendering.

WHAT'S NEXT: HOW VISTLE CAN BE USED BEYOND MERIDIONAL

Beyond MERIDIONAL, Vistle can support the integration of dynamic airflow, CFD and FEM simulations, and expanded operational analysis. Its potential applications include planning and building digital twins of wind parks or architectural prototypes, connecting them with simulation datasets for interactive visualisation of airflow, combustion phenomena, aeroelastic behaviour under different loads and other engineering scenarios, supporting future exploitation across research, industry and sustainable innovation.

Visualisation of turbulence around a wind blade

Find us on **MERIDIONAL EU**

 [meridional.eu](https://www.meridional.eu)

 info@meridional.eu

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.